

BENEFITS OF DAILY READING

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Annotation: Reading helps people feel better and also daily readers enjoy their life more than those who read less. It can improve critical thinking and memory. Some researches indicate that reading also raises brain connectivity and improve individuals' vocabulary and comprehension. This article discusses the benefits of everyday reading and how people can improve this skill.

Key words: skill, reading, books, knowledge, outlook, memory.

Аннотация: Чтение помогает людям чувствовать себя лучше, а ежедневные читатели получают больше удовольствия от жизни, чем те, кто читает меньше. Это может улучшить критическое мышление и память. Некоторые исследования показывают, что чтение также улучшает мозговую связь и улучшает словарный запас и понимание. В этой статье обсуждаются преимущества повседневного чтения и способы улучшения этого навыка.

Ключевые слова: умение, чтение, книги, знания, кругозор, память.

Annotatsiya: O'qish odamlarga o'zlarini yaxshi his qilishlariga yordam beradi va kundalik o'quvchilar kamroq o'qiganlarga qaraganda ko'proq hayotdan zavqlanishadi. Bu tanqidiy fikrlash va xotirani yaxshilashi mumkin. Ba'zi tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'qish, shuningdek, miya aloqasini oshiradi va odamlarning so'z boyligi va tushunishni yaxshilaydi. Ushbu maqolada har kunlik o'qishning afzalliklari va odamlar uchun bu ko'nikmani qanday afzal tomonlari borligi muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: mahorat, o'qish, kitoblar, bilim, dunyoqarash, xotira.

Amongst other things, we have been so preoccupied with social media and the internet that hardly anyone contemplates reading books. While some maybe too

busy to read, others merely don't care to read. There are many benefits to reading, from making you smarter to improve your reading and writing skills [4].

There are plenty of benefits of reading books. Firstly, it is useful and free entertainment that keeps you motivated. When individuals read books, they may relate them to reality while observing their lifetime. While reading readers get to know different characters and situations that help them to see their life from other perspectives. They can compare their life with the events that is in book's. Reading is not only beneficial for literacy but also a good sleep.

Every part of our body needs exercise to stay healthy, and the same goes for our brain. Reading gives it regular exercise and keeps it healthy and sound. Even playing games like chess or solving puzzles results in cognitive stimulation [6]. Reading books is useful for both of your physical and mental health. This habit can aid not only to reduce the stress but also to sleep well. Reading before going to bed is simply one of the best habits that you'll be able to form. This addiction not only betters our sleep but also definitely impacts our whole day's activities through bestowing directly to us a re-energized body and a relaxed mind each morning [5]. By reading, people can increase their general knowledge. It inspires us to be kind and observe other people's feelings. Moreover, reading books teach us to comprehend the world through another person's opinion. Doctors at the Cleveland Clinic suggest reading with your children builds warm and happy associations with books, increasing the likelihood that kids will find reading enjoyable in the future. There are some ways to rise incessant reading.

There are 5 ways to begin and improve daily reading.

1. Set a goal.

In that way students must manage their time and choose appropriate hours for reading. They should begin to read books according to their jobs or hobbies or they select book according to their wishes. If you have any extra time devote it to your favorite books. Moreover, if you want live your life to the fullest or feel like living

another world read historical fiction or fantasy books. With the help of this way you can escape your boring routines.

2. Read in portion.

Readers should divide their books some daily parts. With the help of this way they do not become too tired and bored. Also, they can start reading their books as their habit or as a part of an assignment.

3. Find a good place to read.

Choosing appropriate space for reading is very important because when they enter that place student begin to recall their daily reading. That place should be suitable for reading as it must be beautiful and not boring. When readers are their reading room, they can release their daily tiredness and stress. Also, it is a good idea to read in libraries.

4. Read printed books.

If you do not want your reading will be harmful for your eyes, try to read printed books than reading on devices. Additionally, researches show that people who read paper books can recall easily what they read than reading e-books.

5. Reading audiobooks.

Due to the fact that, 80 percentage of successful people listen audiobooks when they have free time but not convenient for reading. So, the people who want to be rich

or successful they should listen appropriate audiobooks according to their preference.

After setting above mentioned ways, readers can be more responsible for reading every day. They may take notes from their book in order to use in some situations of life. According to the surveys, people who read daily are more clever than other people. The longer the readers read, the more intelligent their mind become. Also, a lot of scientists recommend reading loudly. Because, if a person reads something in loud voice they can understand the story twice. Human brain can imagine and see that. Voice has an ability to make the humans believe. The

interesting fact that even US president Abraham Lincoln's has such kind of habit. He reads newspaper aloud every day.

If you haven't developed this habit yet, it's never too late to start. If you want to set daily reading, you should begin today. Manage your time for reading. More reading also impacts people's words they can sort their words effectively according to the themes.

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